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HOW TO OPEN A BUSINESS IN GERMANY

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КАК ОТКРЫТЬ БИЗНЕС В ГЕРМАНИИ

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GERMANIYADA BIZNES OCHISH QANDAY

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abstract

This publication examines the procedure for starting a business in Germany, the features of various organizational forms, the specifics of opening a business for foreigners, as well as highlights the issues of business insurance and hiring staff.

Bu nashr Germaniyada biznes boshlash tartibini tekshiradi, turli tashkiliy shakllarini xususiyatlari, chet elliklar uchun biznes ochish xususiyatlari, shuningdek biznes sug'urta va ishga xodimlari masalalarini ta'kidlaydi sifatida.

Keywords:

EFTA, GbR, DIHK, HWK.

аннотация

В данной публикации рассматривается процедура открытия бизнеса в Германии, особенности различных организационных форм, специфика открытия бизнеса для иностранцев, а также освещаются вопросы страхования бизнеса и найма персонала.

Ключевые слова:

EFTA, GbR, DIHK, HWK.

Kalit so'zlar:

EFTA, GbR, DIHK, HWK.

annotatsiya

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1. Business development in Germany

More than 100,000 new businesses open in Germany every year. Almost a third of them (30.5%[1]) in 2021 were opened within the information technology sector. Other industries in which businesses are most often opened include healthcare, food

and beverage production, and transport/logistics. Germany ranks 10th in the Global Innovation Index of 2021[2], as well as 22nd in the ranking of countries most favorable for doing business according to the World Bank[3]. There are many reference materials designed to help aspiring entrepreneurs. Foreigners permanently residing in Germany can open their own business. Enterprises owned by foreign companies employ about 3,4 million people in Germany[1] (8% of the total working population).

2. Who can start a business in Germany?

To register a company or register as an individual entrepreneur, citizens of EU / EFTA countries do not need additional permits: they can start a business on the same grounds as residents of Germany. Citizens of non-EU/EFTA countries need to obtain a residence permit in order to register a company or register as an individual entrepreneur, which may require obtaining a visa to enter Germany. The financial requirements for starting a business, as a rule, depend on the type of business being opened. There is a section on financing on the government portal for aspiring entrepreneurs, with which you can determine specific requirements. For some types of business, it may also be necessary to confirm qualifications with licenses/certificates.

3. Possible forms of a legal entity in Germany

Possible forms of a legal entity in Germany can be divided into three categories: Individual entrepreneurs (Einzelunternehmen) Partnerships (Personengesellschaften) Corporations

3.1. Individual entrepreneurs (Einzelunternehmen) These are enterprises managed by one individual, where the business does not exist as a separate legal entity. The owner's personal and professional income are considered together, and the owner is personally responsible for any debts of the business. Individual entrepreneurs in Germany are usually divided into two types: Self-employed entrepreneur (Gewerbetreibender): most types of commercial activity belong to this type, for example, business within the framework of qualified professions, retail trade and production of goods. Gewerbetreibender must be registered in the commercial register of Germany[4]. Freelancer: This type includes business within certain "liberal professions", such as medical, legal, financial, scientific and linguistic professions. For a complete list of liberal professions, you can contact the Institute of Liberal Professions[5]. Freiberufler must register only with the tax inspectorate[6]; registration in the commercial register is not required. The type to which the business belongs is determined by the tax service.

3.2. Partnership (Personengesellschaften) Partnership is a business with two or more owners. To formalize a partnership, as a rule, compliance with minimum formalities is required (for example, the presence of a standard business agreement);

there are no minimum capital requirements. There are various forms of partnership. In Germany, there are the following forms of partnership: Simple partnership, or civil law society (**Gesellschaft des bürgerlichen Rechts - GbR**): the most common form of partnership. Each owner pays income tax on his share of the profits. If the annual turnover of the GbR enterprise exceeds 250,000 euros, a simple partnership must be entered into the commercial register and recognized as an open trading partnership (offene Handelsgesellschaft – OHG). "Limited partnership (EN) – Kommanditgesellschaft – KG (DE)": a partnership in which there is at least one partner bearing full responsibility and at least one limited liability partner not involved in business management (usually an investor). KG must be entered in the commercial register[4] and have a charter. All forms of partnerships, except for "faith partnerships", imply that each of the partnership owners is personally responsible for their share of the business debt.

3.3. Corporations Corporations are enterprises that exist as separate legal entities. Corporations are subject to corporate tax. A corporation may have one or more owners, but each of them is legally classified as an employee (including a director) whose liability is limited to assets invested in the business. All corporations must have a notarized charter, a board of directors/managing director, an entry in the commercial[4] register and a minimum authorized capital. The main types of corporations in Germany include: Limited Liability Company (Gesellschaft mit beschränkter Haftung – GmbH): this is the most common form of German business. The authorized capital of the GmbH must be at least 25,000 euros, half of which must be in the company's bank account at the time of registration. Limited Liability Company of Entrepreneurs (Unternehmergesellschaft – UG). UG is also called Mini-GmbH. UG is a GmbH with an initial minimum authorized capital of 1 euro. The profit from the business is held in reserve until the amount reaches 25,000 euros. After that, UG is recognized by GmbH. Joint Stock Corporation (Aktiengesellschaft – AG): a corporation whose shares are traded on the stock market. AG corporations, as a rule, belong to the category of large companies. The minimum authorized capital is 50,000 euros, while at least 25% of the amount of the authorized capital must be in the company's bank account during registration.

4. How to start a business in Germany for foreigners, first of all, it is necessary to make sure that the business idea is effective. It is worth paying special attention to non-EU/ EFTA citizens applying for a work visa, since in order to obtain a visa, it is necessary to confirm that the business idea will benefit the German economy. Residents of Germany can contact the Unified Contact Center[7] (Netzwerk Einheitlicher Ansprechpartner) (in person or online), which will be able to provide administrative support and advice on the requirements that must be

met to open a business. Recommendations on starting a business can also be found on the government's business portal[8]. Residents of EU/EFTA countries and citizens of non-EU/EFTA countries who have citizenship or permanent residence in Germany, as a rule, can start a business without restrictions on the same conditions as German citizens. It is only necessary to register the business with the relevant authorities (see below). Persons staying on the basis of a visa or a temporary residence permit should familiarize themselves with the visa conditions that allow or prohibit doing business. To open a business in Germany, you may need to obtain a work visa for business and self-employment. Holders of a different type of visa may need to apply for a change in the purpose of the visa through the local migration office[9]. Non-EU/EFTA citizens, in order to move to Germany to open a business or work as a freelancer, usually need to apply for a self-employment work visa, which is valid for three years and can then be extended. Many professions in Germany require special licenses, permits, membership in professional organizations or certificates. Before registering a business, it is necessary to have all the necessary permits. For example: Qualifications/membership in associations for many self-employed Freiberufler, such as doctors, engineers and architects. Trade permits (Gewerbeurlaubnis) for certain types of activities, for example, gambling, insurance brokers or real estate agents. Licenses to open certain categories of businesses, for example, nursing services, catering or taxi companies. Master Craftsman Certificate (Meisterbrief) for qualified artisans. For regulated activities requiring supervision, a certificate of non-conviction (polizeiliches Führungszeugnis) and an extract from the central commercial register (Gewerbezentralregister) are required. These types of activities include the sale of expensive goods, the installation of security systems in buildings, as well as credit or detective agencies. The requirements for starting a business in certain professional fields can be found in the Chamber of Commerce[10] (Deutsche Industrie- und Handelskammer – DIHK), the Chamber of Skilled Crafts[11] (Handwerkskammer – HWK) and the Institute of Liberal Professions[5] (Institut für Freie Berufe – IFB). Some licenses/membership documents may require additional payment.

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